

VOCABULARY STOCK OF THE WRITTEN COMMUNICATIVE
LANGUAGE DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES OF LEXICAL
FEATURES OF ORAL AND WRITTEN ENGLISH IN COMMUNICATION

Makhmudov Khudoyshukur Alisherovich

Ma'mun University NEI,
Faculty of "Philology" Department of
"Roman-German Philology", Teacher

Abstract: His article is devoted to some challenges that can occur in a variety languages when pronouncing the linguistic utterances, their formation and their usage in communication.

Keywords: The descriptive approach to the Language, The Theory of Constituency and Recursion, The theory of Modularity, The descriptive approach to the Language

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена проблемам, которые могут возникнуть в разных языках при произношении лингвистических слов и при их употреблении и образовании в общении

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада лингвистик сўзларни талаффуз қилишда ва уларни мулоқотда қўллашда ва шакллантиришда турли тилларда юзага келиши мумкин бўлган муоммаларга тўхталиб ўтилган

Ключевой слова: Описательный подход к языку, Теория конституции и рекурсии, Теория модульности, Описательный подход к языку

Калит сўзлар: Тилга тафсифий ёндашув, Конституция ва рекурсия назарияси, Модуллиқ назарияси,

Writing systems, or scripts, can be classified by which units of language are graphically represented. In logographic systems, each grapheme, or individual written symbol, represents a particular morpheme or word. In syllabic systems, each symbol

represents a particular syllable. And in alphabetic systems, each letter represents a particular sound or phoneme. Of course, these categories are simplifications of a more complex reality! Logographic systems often have some phonetic elements which refer to sounds in the spoken language. Syllabic scripts frequently “cheat” by using diacritics to indicate consonant quality or vowel length. Alphabets sometimes treat vowels differently from consonants, and no alphabet has a perfect one-to-one correspondence between letter and phoneme. Most scripts do not neatly fit into one particular category, in part because they are evolving systems, adapted from and influenced by the scripts of surrounding speech communities.

English spelling

The spelling of many English words does not consistently correspond to their pronunciation, in part because English spelling was established before the Great Vowel Shift (see Chapter 8) changed the pronunciation of many English words. In fact, English spelling diverges from the phonemic principle in just about every way possible:

- A language may represent a given phoneme with a combination of letters (digraphs): e.g. ship, knit, and chin
- A language may represent one phoneme with different letters or combinations of letters: e.g. home, boat, though
- A language may represent different phonemes with the same letter or combination of letters: e.g. read (present tense), read (past tense), red
- A language may retain unpronounced letters from earlier pronunciations: e.g. “silent e” (home, ripe, tame) and “silent k” (knight, kneel).
- Different dialects of a language may pronounce different phonemes for the same word: e.g. the different pronunciations of neither and either

Conservatism Because of its permanency, writing is a conservative tool; it allows “repeated inspection, verification, and comment” (Coulmas 2003: 225). It selectively preserves certain information (while unwritten information fades), as recognized in the old adage that “History is written by the victors.” What gets written (and reproduced)

becomes a part of the culture – its history, literary canons, religious doctrine, and civil laws.

Democratization

Technologies of writing, especially the invention of the printing press and moveable type, played an important role in the democratization of literacy. Through the Middle Ages, scrolls and books could only be reproduced by hand. Illuminated manuscripts (mostly of religious texts) were copied in monasteries, which also served as repositories of knowledge. However, the emphasis was on preservation of knowledge, not discovery of new knowledge.

Standardization Writing is also an important tool for language standardization. Writing systems are inherently conservative; the effort to establish conventional pairings between an inventory of graphemes and the sounds (or syllables or morphemes) they represent is considerable, and changes face stiff resistance. For example, despite its many irregularities (see the sidebar above on ‘English spelling’), attempts to reform English spelling have been unsuccessful. Major innovations typically have occurred when one speech community borrowed the writing system of another, free of much of its prior cultural baggage.

Writing is a tool which extends and amplifies many of the functions of spoken language. Just as archaeologists can learn a lot about a culture by analyzing its tools, we can learn a lot about cultures and their languages by understanding their writing systems. Writing systems developed within the constraints of the structure of their spoken language to meet the communicative needs of their speech community. Each kind of writing system – logographic, syllabic, alphabetic, and consonantal alphabetic – is the product of a complex balance between form and function. As speech communities have developed, so too have their writing systems, responding to new needs and facilitating or hastening some social changes. Logographic systems, in which each written sign represents a morpheme in the spoken language, are formally appropriate to languages, like Chinese, with little inflectional morphology. They help

to unify speech communities with broad dialect variation; even when speakers of mutually unintelligible dialects pronounce a word very differently, they can read the same word symbol. In syllabic writing systems, each written symbol represents a syllable of the spoken language, though most syllabic systems use additional diacritic symbols to indicate additional phonetic information. Syllabic systems are particularly well suited to languages, like Japanese, with simple syllables (and a limited syllable inventory). In alphabetic systems, like Hangul and English, the written symbols represent the phonemes of the spoken language. (In consonantal alphabets, like Arabic, only consonants are represented by letters.) Because they represent the smallest meaningful units of meaning, alphabetic systems were easily adapted to new languages. Writing developed from pictograms which were direct representations of objects in the world, using primary symbolization. With the leap to secondary symbolization in Sumerian cuneiform, written forms directly represented some units of the spoken language (phonemes, syllables, or words), and referred to objects and concepts in the world only through the spoken language. Over centuries, Egyptian hieroglyphics developed a consonantal alphabet which successive dominant cultures – the Phoenicians, the Greeks, and the Romans – adapted to their own languages. Writing has played a profound role in the development of literate human cultures – although its effects sometimes seem contradictory. On one hand, writing exerts a conservative force – sustaining social orders by preserving their histories, laws, and values. For centuries, controlling access to literacy preserved a monopoly on most domains of knowledge for the privileged few. Writing has even slowed language change, by freezing earlier pronunciations and setting prescriptive grammatical standards. On the other hand, increasing literacy in many speech communities has facilitated social change. And the knowledge preserved in writing has been distributed more and more widely by new technologies – first print and more recently the computer and the internet. Perhaps the most profound effect of writing on modern cultures has been the way we think about knowledge itself. As Douglas Biber (1988; 3) has pointed out, “The permanency of

writing . . . confronts us with the incorrect ‘knowledge’ of earlier generations and thereby fosters a critical attitude towards knowledge.” Writing has fostered the advance of knowledge by forcing us to confront prior conceptions and continually question our own beliefs.

The simplest grammars are called regular expressions. Regular expressions can model morphological phenomena, for example. Anything modeled by regular expressions can in turn be modeled by context-free grammars as well. However, there are phenomena (for example, center-embedded sentences like *The little puppy the boy the principal hated loved ran away*) that can’t be modeled by regular expressions but can be modeled by context-free grammars. So context-free grammars are more expressive than regular expressions; they can model everything that regular expressions can model, and more. In turn, there are phenomena in natural language that can’t be accounted for by context-free grammars but can be handled by a context-sensitive grammar (Shieber 1985). Context-sensitive grammars can model everything a context-free grammar can express, and more. Context-sensitive grammars, in turn, cannot represent certain formal patterns which another class of grammars, the aptly named “unrestricted grammars,” can express. It turns out that for every level of grammatical expressiveness in the Chomsky hierarchy there is an analogous computing device, as shown in the figure below. Thus, regular expressions are equivalent to finite-state machines. Context-free grammars are equivalent to machines called push-down automata. Context-sensitive grammars are equivalent to machines called linear-bounded automata. And unrestricted grammars are equivalent to Turing Machines. The Church–Turing thesis, which has yet to be disproved, proposes that this is the limit to computable complexity.

Differences and similarities of lexical features of oral and written English in communication

Everyone knows that language can be used to express meaning, but it is not easy to define meaning. One problem is that there are several dimensions of meaning.

Imagine that I ask you, “Can you give me an apple?” while looking at a bowl of apples on the table beside you. What I literally asked is whether you have the ability to give me an apple; this is the semantic meaning of what I said. Sometimes people will make an annoying joke by responding only to the semantic meaning of such a question; they’ll just answer, “Yes, I can.” But what I almost certainly want is for you to give me one of the apples next to you, and I expect you to know that this is what I want. This speaker’s meaning is what I intend to communicate, and it goes beyond the literal, semantic meaning of what I said. Linguists study both semantic meaning and speaker’s meaning. Let’s look at semantic meaning first. To understand semantic meaning, we have to bring together three main components: the context in which a sentence is used, the meanings of the words in the sentence, and its morphological and syntactic structure. For example, suppose you say to me: (1) My dog chased a cat under the house. Because (1) contains the pronoun *my*, part of its meaning depends on the fact that you uttered it. Since you uttered it, *my* refers to you. So to some extent the semantic meaning of a sentence depends on the context of use – the situation in which the sentence was uttered, by a particular speaker, to a particular addressee, at a particular time, and so forth. The semantic meaning of (1) also depends on the meanings of the individual words *dog*, *chased*, *a*, *cat*, etc.; therefore, semantic meaning depends on the lexicon of English. In addition, the morphological and syntactic structure of sentence (1) is crucial to its meaning. If the words were rearranged to *A cat under the house chased my dog*, it would mean something different. So semantic meaning depends on the grammatical structure of the sentence. Now let’s think about the speaker’s meaning of (1). Suppose that you know I’ve lost my cat and you say (1) to me. In that case, it would be likely that your speaker’s meaning is to inform me that my cat may be hiding under the house, and to suggest that I go there to look for it. To understand where this meaning comes from, we need to bring together two components. First, the semantic meaning is certainly part of the picture; there is some kind of connection between your saying that your dog chased a cat under the house and your suggesting that I look for

my lost cat under the house. But in order for me to understand your speaker's meaning, I have to assume that we both know my cat is missing, that you know I want to find it, and that you want to see that my cat is safely back home. These are additional aspects of the context of use which help to determine your speaker's meaning. We can visualize the two kinds of meaning as follows¹:

Semantics focuses on the link between the lexicon and the grammar and semantic meaning. Pragmatics focuses on the connection between context of use and both semantic and speaker's meaning.

Fundamental semantic concepts and compositionality

The most fundamental semantic concepts describe how words, phrases, and sentences relate to each other and to the world. Synonymy. Two words, phrases, or sentences are synonyms if they have the same semantic meaning. I saw more than two and fewer than five dogs is synonymous with I saw three or four dogs. Antonymy. Two words are antonyms if they are opposed in semantic meaning. Tall and short are antonyms. Hyponymy. A word is a hyponym of another if its semantic meaning is more specific than the other's. Dog is a hyponym of animal.

Hypernymy. A word is a hypernym of another if its semantic meaning is more general than the other's. Animal is a hypernym of dog. Ambiguity. A word, phrase, or sentence is ambiguous if it has multiple semantic meanings. Bank is ambiguous (river

¹ Fasold R.W. Connor-Linton J. and co-authors. An Introduction to Language and Linguistics. –Cambridge. –P.139.
WWW.HUMOSCIENCE.COM

bank vs. financial institution). Entailment. A sentence entails another if the truth of the first guarantees the truth of the second. I like all animals entails I like pigs. Tautology. A sentence is a tautology if it must be true. If something is a big animal, it's an animal is a tautology. Contradicts. A sentence contradicts another if they can't both be true. I like pigs contradicts I hate all animals. Contradiction. A sentence is a contradiction if it cannot be true. That is a big animal, and it's not an animal is a contradiction. (Intuitively, a contradiction is a sentence that contradicts itself.) These concepts allow us to talk about meaning. With them we can say things like "The Warlpiri sentence (2) is ambiguous; it can mean a big dog or the big dog is chasing me." You learned in previous chapters that grammar (morphology and syntax) generate novel words, phrases, and sentences – in fact, an infinite number of them. This gives us an infinite number of words, phrases, and sentences that can have meaning. In order to explain how an infinite number of pieces of language can be meaningful, and how we, as language users, can figure out the meanings of new ones every day, semanticists apply the Principle of Compositionality. The Principle of Compositionality: The semantic meaning of any unit of language is determined by the semantic meanings of its parts along with the way they are put together. According to the Principle of Compositionality, the meaning of a sentence like Mary liked you is determined by (a) the meanings of the individual morphemes that make it up (Mary, like, you, "past") and (b) the morphological and syntactic structures of the sentence. The Principle of Compositionality doesn't just apply to sentences. It also implies that the meaning of the verb phrase liked you is determined by the meanings of its parts and the grammatical structure of the verb phrase, and that the meaning of the word liked is determined by the meanings of the two morphemes that make it up (like and (e)d). The subfield of semantics known as compositional semantics (or formal semantics) is especially concerned with how the Principle of Compositionality applies, and consequently formal semanticists study the variety of grammatical patterns which occur in individual languages and across the languages of the world. Formal semantics

developed in linguistics during the early 1970s under the influence of philosophers, especially Richard Montague².

Idioms There are some phrases which are exceptions to compositionality. An idiom is a phrase whose meaning is not what you'd expect given the meanings of the words making it up. In other words, idioms are not compositional: keep an eye on X, get a handle on X, and kick the bucket do not get their meaning exclusively from the meanings of their parts and the way they are put together. Idioms often get their meanings from metaphorical interpretations, often lost in the mists of history, but the case of get a handle on X is fairly clear; one might put a handle on a physical object to make it easier to carry, and to understand something is, metaphorically, to be able to carry it around in one's mind. Once one already knows what this idiom means, the choice of handle makes sense, but it can be very difficult to understand an idiom the first time one hears it. We typically need help to understand a new idiom, and once we do understand it, we remember its meaning as a complete pattern. What are some other idioms in English or in another language which you are familiar with? How do you know what they mean?

References

1. Fasold R.W. Connor-Linton J. and co-authors. *An Introduction to Language and Linguistics*. –Cambridge. –P.139.
2. Montague, R. 1974, *Formal philosophy: selected papers of Richard Montague*, ed. R. H. Thomason, New Haven: Yale University Press.
3. The New York Times Book Review, Nov. 17, 1963.
4. New Statesman, 22 Feb. 1963, p. 27|,
5. Galperin I.R *Stylistics*. Moscow: Higher School, 1971